

HOLY MEMORY IS ETERNAL COURAGE

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Annotation. This article reflects the idea that the Day of Remembrance and Honor is widely celebrated in Uzbekistan on May 9, that human memory is sacred, and that the memory of the victims of World War II is eternal.

Keywords: memory, dignity, war victims, war veterans, victory, statue of a grieving mother, human memory, human dignity, courage, eternity.

HUMAN MEMORY IS SACRED, HUMAN DIGNITY IS GREAT.

May 9 - This national holiday, declared the Day of Remembrance and Honor on the initiative of the First President Islam Karimov, is widely celebrated in our country every year. During the years of independence, this day has become an important historical date, which literally restored justice to human memory and dignity, and embodied the original truth.

Memory and appreciation are the unique spiritual blessings of the human mind, the eternal criteria of life. The qualities of patronage, generosity and generosity, kindness and benevolence are intertwined with the concepts of memory and dignity. After all, only people whose hearts are full of generosity, love and compassion will always remember their history and ancestors, and will appreciate their selfless compatriots, those who work for a bright future.

It is significant that in these days, when the 61st anniversary of the victory over fascism in World War II is being celebrated, the Day of Remembrance and Honor is being celebrated in our country with special attention. Consequently, the courage and service of our compatriots in ensuring the historic victory in World War II was incomparable. We will never forget the courage and devotion of thousands of Uzbek boys who gave their lives in the war, who worked day and night behind the front lines and shared their food with others.

Man, people, nation are alive, alive with historical memory. It is both our duty and our duty to remember and appreciate the good deeds of the past. In this sense, remembering and honoring the memory of thousands of our compatriots who died in World War II, the people who have endured heavy fighting, returned our wounded, contributed to the victory with their hard work behind the front lines. , it is especially gratifying that the honoring and worthy rewarding of our mothers has become one of our national values.

Most importantly, in the minds of our young people, human qualities such as the memory of the past, the appreciation of the living are becoming more and more entrenched. Remembering the lessons of yesterday, the people who sacrificed their lives for the future of our people, teaches us to value today and tomorrow. Without memory, there is no appreciation. These notions have become a special spiritual value for the generation of independence. But, in the words of our Head of State, the great victory was ensured by great courageous people, and we, the grateful generations, will always honor these selfless compatriots and bow before their incomparable tenacity and memory.

Every year on May 9, the Memorial Square in the capital will be busier than ever. It is attended by war and labor veterans, members of the government, deputies and senators, the military, and members of the public. Silent music echoes across the square. The golden pages of the Book of Remembrance, in which the names of our compatriots who died in the war are forever sealed, testify to the fate of the selfless sons of the Motherland. The head of state lays a wreath at the foot of the statue of the grieving mother to the sound of a military band. Respecting the memory of thousands of our compatriots who died in the Second World War, the First President said: "Today, May 9, I congratulate all our compatriots on the national holiday called the Day of

Remembrance and Honor in our country. while giving thanks for the prosperous days, he rightly bows before the memory of our ancestors who gave their lives in the struggle for the peace and tranquility of our lives, for the purity of our skies. At the same time, life today, the war veterans living among us, deserve our full respect. ”

The people of Uzbekistan, along with many other nations, made a significant contribution to the victory over fascism in World War II. At that time, our country had a population of about 3.5 million, of which about 1.5 million were mobilized for war. For the freedom and liberty of our Motherland, for the peaceful life we live today, more than 400,000 of our compatriots have died on the battlefields, and many more are missing. It's heartbreaking to think that so many people have been killed. After all, the only person killed in battle is Man. Her life came to an abrupt end, and her dreams did not come true. There is much more grief, sorrow, and sorrow behind this loss. Widows and orphans, the hopes and sorrows of a mother who looks at the path of her child, are at the root of this bitter loss ... In this sense, the endless tragedies that this war has inflicted on humanity will never be forgotten. The courage and tenacity shown by millions of people on the battlefields and behind the front lines will remain in our history, in the memory of our people.

Our first President noted that not only is there a threat of war in the world today, but also that this threat is growing day by day: “Despite the fact that in its history mankind has repeatedly witnessed that war has never brought relief to anyone, , It is sad that the number of those who want war on earth is not decreasing. The aftermath of the war in Afghanistan, which began 27 years ago, is far from over, and there is still no peace and stability in the country. The war in Iraq and the reality of the war around Iran are also worrying. Why do such war-torn efforts continue? Unfortunately, it is difficult to find an answer to this question. Because the history of the world has shown that neither those who started the war nor those who survived the war have ever been relieved. So the question is, what can be done to prevent wars? To do this, first of all, we need to ensure today's and tomorrow's life based on peace and stability in the world and in our region. Any problem along the way must be resolved peacefully, through diplomacy. The efforts of our country in this direction are of special importance. Our people believe that the signing of the Alliance Agreement with Russia, as well as the agreements on further deepening friendly and cooperative relations with major countries such as China, South Korea, India and Pakistan, are important steps for peace and development in Uzbekistan. first of all, our youth must have a deep understanding.

Most importantly, each of us must always be alert, sensitive, and vigilant. At the same time, we must learn to live our lives not as indifferent and indifferent observers, but as direct fighters for peace and tranquility, a prosperous life and development, - said the First President. First of all, our young people need to study history in depth. Because a society that doesn't know its history can't find a way to the future. A nation without history has no future. Over the centuries of history, Uzbekistan has not seen many invasions, what storms the Central Asian region has not been in, who has not tried to make us dependent and dependent. If we do not learn from this history, tomorrow's events will happen again tomorrow. In other words, a society that draws the right conclusions from yesterday will move forward with confidence. At the same time, young people should not only study history, but also be proud of our great past. Because this is our history. They are the glorious life of our great ancestors, such as Amir Temur, our great scholars and thinkers. Let's not forget that it is not enough for today's people, especially for the builders of our great future, to be proud of our history. As the heirs of the ancestors who made a great history, our proud and courageous young people must live in the consciousness of the concept and aspiration: "What do I leave for the next generation?" As we build on our achievements, we need to strive to stand out from the crowd. Then we can have a great future. In fact, the same aspiration is at the heart of the call that we have never been, are, and will never be inferior to anyone.

The oldest participants in World War II are now over eighty. Last year, 33,572 war veterans celebrated the same date with us on the ground. Until this holiday, 22,251 of them remained. Let's honor and respect our veterans while they are alive. It should be both a duty and a duty for today's generation to do everything we can to prolong the lives of war veterans, even for a year or a month, to comfort them, to cure their pain. It has been seven years since we started celebrating this date

as the Day of Remembrance and Honor, the President concluded. In the past, this holiday was widely celebrated by people of all nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country. In this sense, it is great that these vital ideas, such as bowing to the memory of the past, honoring people in life, are ingrained in the blood of our people and today have become an integral part of the life of every citizen, a sacred value for all of us. is an event.

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